

„Ingenieure der Verlautbarung. Kommunikationspraktiken des
Bundeskanzleramtes in der Entstehungsphase der deutschen
Mediendemokratie in den 1950er und 1960er Jahren

Engineers of political announcement. Practices of political communication
in the Federal Chancellery regarding media and the public in early West
German democracy (1949-1969)

Prof. Dr. Angela Schwarz (University of Siegen)
PD Dr. Heiner Stahl (University of Siegen)

Project funded by the Minister of State for Culture and Media (Mrs. Monika
Grütters), 2017-2021.

*„Was der Kommunismus tut, um eine schlechte Herrschaft mit propagandistischen Mitteln zu
befestigen, das sollten wir in Freiheit tun, um durch die Entfaltung der geistigen und moralischen
Kräfte unseres Volkes der bestmöglichen Demokratie eine überzeugte Gefolgschaft zu geben.“¹*

What communism does in terms of agitation and propaganda, making an evil reign firm, is what we
ought to do likewise, in freedom and liberty, in order to unfold the spiritual and moral forces of our
Volk providing a strong and confident public of followers for our way to and appreciation of
‘democracy’.

Otto Lenz, a Christian Democratic Union-politician, wrote this passage in a preface to an opinion
poll published in 1956. This survey, conducted by the Institute für Demoskopie Allensbach², deals
with notions of social reality and the appreciation of socio-economic status in postwar West

¹ Lenz, Otto: Vorwort, in: Institut für Demoskopie (Hg.): Die soziale Wirklichkeit. Aus einer Untersuchung des
Instituts für Demoskopie, Allensbach : Verlag für Demoskopie, 1956, S. 7-16, S. 16.

² URL: <http://www.ifd-allensbach.de/service/english/summary.html> [26.6.2017].

Germany. This quotation sheds light on the political framing of democracy within the semantics of Cold War Culture. The lines does also illuminate how the key concepts of NS-Propaganda like ‚Volk‘ and ‚Gefolgschaft‘ were made convenient for a rather nationalist, anticommunist reading of West Germany as strong and defensive democratic society. A decade after capitulation of May 1945 features of the *Lingua Tertii Imperii*³, language of the Third Reich, are still avering presence in the semantic field of public communication. Lenz’ statement demonstrates the instability of democratic values in the mental maps of postwar politicians in Germany. Opinion leaders like Lenz, former Secretary of State in Konrad Adenauers’ Chancellery (1951-1953), supervising several initiatives in restructuring the media policies in the Federal Republic of Germany, continue to consider the mechanisms and practices of propaganda as a valuable asset for public relations in the 1950s West Germany. Being trained in the press relations department of the Prussian Ministry of Justice (1929-1933), Lenz gained professional knowledge in terms of engineering of official announcements. After working in law department of the Prussian Ministry of Commerce and Trade, Lenz moved to managing a regional court of law until late 1930s. Nationalsocialist reorganization of the juridical system disbanded him from this position in 1938, he then became a partner in a Berlin based law firm. Following the July 20 1944-plot against Hitler and his entourage, Lenz served a sentence in Brandenburg-Görden. This experience laid the foundation for him engaging in postwar German politics and in considering democracy as an eligible political system. But this move towards becoming a democratic politician did not include to refrain from modes of forming and manipulating public opinion. Tactics of propaganda were deeply rooted in Lenz political socialization and his understanding of communicating to diverse target audiences within mass society.

Kontaktzone Bonn. Die Praktiken öffentlicher Kommunikation und der Verlautbarung in der bundesrepublikanischen Mediendemokratie (1949-1969) is conducted by Prof. Dr. Angela Schwarz (Chair of Modern History at the University of Siegen) and Dr. Heiner Stahl. The 36 month research project is funded by the Minister of State for Culture and Media, Mrs. Monika Grütters. In November 2016 she has announced a major research programme to examining the presence and impact of NSDAP-party members in the Federal Chancellery, Ministries and others federal bureaucracies.⁴ *Kontaktzone* explores the practices of official press relations at the federal executive level of West German government and examines the conditions of exchange and influencing that has been established between journalists, correspondents, politicians and experts of political

³ Klemperer, Victor: *LTI. Notizen eines Philologen*, Berlin : Aufbau, 1947.

⁴ Siehe URL: <https://www.bundesregierung.de/Content/DE/Pressemitteilungen/BPA/2017/08/2017-08-14-bkm-aufarbeitung-ns.html> [Letzter Zugriff 16.9.2017].

communication in the two decades from 1949 to 1969.

The central pitch of this study is: different portfolio of knowledge related to propaganda and public relations are competitive in these two decades of re-initiating democracy and public debate in postwar Germany. The research is aiming at priming the definitions and practices of public relations, press relations, political communication and propaganda. How did these stocks of knowledge change in this period, how did the procedures of communicating official information adjust to the shifting perception of ‘the public’? How strong and lasting were the modes of public relations knowledge transferred from the Western allies to the spaces of politics and public debate in post-1945 Germany? What elements of official information policy in West Germany did refer to a portfolio of propaganda and strategies of announcement to the local and regional press that were forged between 1900 and 1950? In what ways are the practices of public communication in Germany tied to the experience of party press in Weimar Republic and the successful centralizing initiatives of the Ministry of Propaganda and Public Enlightenment under Josef Goebbels and what sort of impact could the new media policies of the allied military and civil government – especially in terms of licensing and issuing concessions for publishers – exercise in this newly shaped landscape of media

The archival stocks of the Federal Chancellery (Koblenz), personal literary remains of party politicians of the Christian Democratic Union, the Social Democratic Party and the Liberal Democrats. In addition to these sources the project explores the correspondence of journalists, publishers as well as General Directors of federal broadcasting stations with the media experts and press relations officers at the Federal Chancellery.